

Metadata Standards and Practices: Lessons Learned from Interviews with Experts

Abstract:

Data is difficult to reuse without consistent metadata, making it difficult to decipher and reuse dataset and analysis scripts. Our team is working on solutions at the variable level, including the so called Variable Object Identification (VOI) system. This Summer 2024 project included interviews with 35 researchers and digital infrastructure providers about “metadata”: current concepts, community needs, currently available tools, and the future of the field. Based on 17 questions, it explored aspects such as variable naming, data reuse problems, transparency and potential solutions including suggestions for standard tools. Online Qualitative Case Study interviews (~1-hour interviews) were recorded, transcribed and analyzed, identifying major themes and mentioned data standards such as RDA, BIDS, DDI, GESIS and Frictionless. The results indicate an awareness of the problems, a limited number of initiatives at the variable level, and difficulties in encouraging the use of standards, despite their potential in standardizing analytical scripts.

Keywords: meta.data, qualitative data analysis, interviews, digital infrastructure.

Metadata Standards and Practices: Lessons Learned from Interviews with Experts

With the exponential growth of data generation, the importance of meta.data, which describes the raw data and potentially enables its efficient retrieval, analysis and integration, is growing. However, the lack of standards at the variable level significantly hinders the practical use of these capabilities, forcing time-consuming recoding processes and limiting data interoperability (Buttliere, 2021). Standardization of metadata, variable naming, and the development of ‘plug and play’ datasets and analysis scripts are key steps in improving data quality, consistency, and usability, especially in the social sciences, environmental sciences, and healthcare. The introduction of standardized conventions and quality indicators associated with the Variable Object Identifier (VOI) system allows for the creation of reliable and comparable datasets and searchable data repositories, which supports the rapid and regular publication of results and speeds up analysis processes while maintaining high quality.

Problems with standardization and coding of variables

Inconsistency in variable coding is a significant problem, making it difficult to integrate data from different sources despite the existing FAIR framework (Jacobsen et al., 2020) and fostering time-consuming data cleaning before analysis (Groom et al., 2019). Standardized naming conventions and coding schemes are identified as key tools to improve communication and understanding of data (Buttliere, 2021; Lipski et al., 2021). At the same time, inadequate documentation of metadata limits the possibility of reuse, as highlighted in a study by Huang et al. (2021). Interdisciplinary data sharing is also an important aspect. Centralized, project-specific metadata platforms can enhance interoperability and promote cross-discipline collaboration by providing a unified metadata management framework (Child et al., 2022). The metadata ecosystem concept, proposed by Jacob (2024), supports data sharing in the FAIR network and further emphasizes the importance of a collaborative approach.

These studies point to the need to implement standards, tools and platforms to support better data management across scientific disciplines, which significantly increases data usability and reliability. Lee et al. (2023) also emphasized the importance of standardized codebooks in data analysis (there EHR), ensuring consistent definition of variables across studies. Standardization of

variable naming plays an equally important role in ensuring interoperability of datasets. Nogueira (2021) showed that standardized variable naming significantly affects (there cluster analysis) results, which is particularly important in interdisciplinary studies where integration of data from different sources is necessary. Common naming conventions increase the usability and ease of integration and allow for e.g., searchable data repositories and plug and play analysis scripts (Buttliere, 2021).

Many potential solutions to support standardization of variables

Thousands of data repositories have sprung up in recent years, with the re3data.org repository of repository containing more than 4,000 repositories, but the most efficient way to access datasets remains the use of direct-link publications, which limits access to unpublished data and reduces its usefulness. Meta.data standards introduced as part of the open data movement require users to create new meta.data for each collection, making the process time-consuming and inconsistent. There is a lack of tools that allow existing coding schemes for variables to be transferred between datasets (Buttliere, 2023). As a result, repositories are difficult to search, and “plug and play” analyses don't work because of coding differences. High effort and low resultant value further limit the adoption of meta.data standards.

All of these problems stem from the fact that variables are not systematically tagged in datasets (Buttliere, 2021). Even if your team and our team measure age in the same way (e.g., by the number of days since birth), we don't code it in the dataset in the same way, which means we can't share datasets. Some scientific fields are already implementing innovative tools to address metadata challenges and improve metadata quality and consistency. One example is the dmdScheme tool (Krug & Petchey, 2020), which allows researchers to create metadata schemas tailored to the specific needs of their field. As the authors describe, the solution supports the iterative development of metadata schemas through user-friendly interfaces such as web applications and spreadsheets. The approach promotes flexibility, quality assessment and validation of metadata, adapting it to changing research requirements. In the field of proteomics, the Human Proteome Organization Proteomics Standard Initiative (HUPO-PSI), described by Perez-Riverola (2020), has established standardized file formats containing metadata specific to different types of proteomics data. This makes research more uniform and reproducible, and makes data sharing between teams much easier. Similarly, in systems biology,

the Microbench tool, described by Lubbock and Lopez (2022), automates the process of metadata management in Python code. This makes it easy for researchers to capture standards-compliant metadata, which increases the reproducibility of results and promotes better research practices. Our team also recently released the R package `meta.data()`, which allows researchers to create and share meta.data templates for commonly used variables (Buttliere, 2023).

Lacking an overview of the literature and field and best potential avenues for the future.

Our team set out to explore ways to standardize the coding of variables most commonly used by researchers and data analysis by creating templates and standard methods for describing them, making it easier to search repositories and automate data analysis (Buttliere, 2021; Buttliere, 2023). As part of this effort, the `meta.data()` package in R was developed to allow researchers to create, share and reuse variable templates. The package supports the export of CSV files containing meta.data fields such as `full.text`, `associated.ids`, `scale.values` and `missing.indicator`. The tool, based on the Variable Object Identifier system (Buttliere, 2023), aims to improve standardization and collaboration in data management.

This study - interviews with experts, field leaders, and tool makers.

In order to understand what is going on in the area, we ran a study interviewing people in this area, especially meta.data standards and tool makers, as well as researchers from different disciplines, to get an overview of the existing practices and also where these people think the field should go. Finally, we also wanted to hear what they thought about our ideas, so we also asked them what they thought about e.g., the template/ VOI system. Thus, aside from hearing their approaches, part of the interview was also based on presenting our solution and hearing their reactions, as well as exploring potential collaborations.

We conducted 35 online video interviews with various participants in this space, to determine needs as well as what is actually being done and how we can all work together better. The semi-structured interviews consisted of 17 questions on the state of the art, the problems, and potential future solutions including our own. This paper presents the main conclusions we drew from these interviews.

Sample

Since our team was principally focused on the latest developments in the area of meta.data across a wide range of disciplines and localities, we searched across the entire area for potential interviewees. Participants were recruited through email; we looked for individuals on projects that we knew about or could find online and snowballed the sample from there. For instance, we were keen to include interviewees from organizations like the Data Documentation Initiative, the Brain Imaging Data Structure, the Frictionless community, and WikiData. We then looked at these websites and asked the interviewees if they could recommend people to interview next. To find potential respondents, we also used OSF, researchgate and our pool of collaborators. We wanted to reach people who analyze data on a daily basis and have experience with data management, as well as those people who are actively creating standards and or tools for certain groups and teams, disciplines, etc.

Recordings and Transcripts

The meetings were hosted on the Google Meets platform and recorded using Open Broadcasting Software (v. 30.2.3). The interviews were done between July and early September 2024. The duration of the interviews was between 30 minutes and 60 minutes. The videos of the interviews can be seen online at the OSF along with the other data. Unfortunately, two interviews had corrupted data, though in general the ideas from that interview are incorporated, though there is no transcript (the video had no audio). Videos and transcripts are available here <https://osf.io/xe985/>.

For transcribing the discussions we used TurboScribe, which utilizes Whisper, an AI-powered speech-to-text transcription technology known for achieving a word error rate comparable to human-level performance ([Radford et al., 2022](#)). Due to organizational issues the four last interviews had to be transcribed using Restream, a similar, but free AI- powered software. The transcripts are available at osf.io/xe985. Transcripts were read for accuracy and to review the material.

Materials & main questions

The interviews were semi-structured and discussion based, with a set of 17 key questions that we hoped to get answers to throughout the course of the discussion. These questions are grouped into several categories including: 1. experiences/ state of the art, 2. how they code their variables and metadata, 3. examination of problems during the reuse scenario, 4. potential solutions regarding data

sharing and reuse, and 5. thoughts about variable specific templates (VOI system) for metadata. As the interviews had a conversational form, often several questions were covered at once during a longer comment from the interviewee.

The types of questions we aimed to ask were open ended, with a few exceptions of yes/no questions which were designed to elicit some further elaboration. An excellent example is number 2. Have you ever shared your datasets? If so, how do you make your data reusable to others? This may seem like a basic question, but in fact we were asking participants at the very cutting edge of the field, and across many fields (e.g., biology, psychology, economics). Another example of this sort of question is number 7. When using other researchers' datasets, did you have any problems using their variables? What were the problems that you encountered? These are so called 'yes and' questions which are also designed to elicit further discussion from the participant.

The questions also sought specific answers as to e.g., how the participants coded their variables, or what exactly their ideal reuse scenario looks like. These questions are also designed to help us build the meta.data template system. A portion of the interview asked them what they think about meta.data templates and the VOI system for specific variables, uses they could imagine for such templates, and what a tool or system that used such templates would or could look like. These are questions which we expect to inform the system that we are building.

Table 1*Materials used during the interview.*

Background and meta.data state of the art	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Can you briefly summarize your work -> How does metadata relate to your work? (For instance how do you use it, is it a concept in your life, what do you know about it, etc.) 2. Have you ever shared your datasets? If so, how do you make your data reusable to others? 3. Are there any variables in your area that nearly everybody uses? How are these variables coded into the datasets, is there a standard method you use? (You can think of condition, participant id, particular scales for personality, etc.) 4. How do you name your variables and, for instance, indicate missing data? Is this the standard way in your field? 5. Do you have a specific coding scheme for meta.data when creating datasets? 6. Do you use meta.data guides or analysis scripts from external sources? If so, where do you look for them?
Establishing the Problems	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 7. When using other researchers' datasets, did you have any problems using their variables? What were the problems that you encountered? 8. Why do you think people do not use standard encodings for their variables? 9. Can you imagine ways that using meta.data templates for commonly used variables could make your work easier? What are they? (e.g., standard analysis scripts.)
Potential solutions	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 10. What do you feel are potential solutions to getting people to use standard variable encodings? 11. How would you establish meta.data templates within your specific research area? 12. From your perspective, what kind of infrastructure do you think would be needed to make it so people can use these standard encodings? What would such a tool or service do? 13. What are the features that any standardized template should include? 14. How do you imagine the ideal data reuse scenario? How can this be achieved? 15. Can you see yourself using meta.data templates and standard analysis scripts? How and why would you use them? 16. What variables would you most value templates for? Would you be willing to help create them? 17. Would you like to help us make common metadata templates for your field ? (We are searching for area partners for something like a consortium.

All participants were given the chance to say any concluding remarks to the final question: Is there anything else you would like to say on this topic before we finish?

Geographic distribution of the sample.

These interviews were focused on gathering the opinions of the most relevant experts and so were conducted across different world regions. The distribution of these interviews is outlined in Table 1 below. Overall, you can see that most of the participants came from Europe, though approximately 30% of the interviews were done with North Americans and lesser participation from the other groups.

Table 2
Geographical Sample Description

	World Region (number of countries)		Female	Male	Area/Field of the people from that region
1	Asia	China, India, United Arab Emirates, Japan	4	0	Psychology
2	Europe	Germany, UK, France, Poland, Norway	10	10	Economics, interface/R package, psychology, economics/taxes, neuroscience, statistics, biology, sociology
3	North America	USA, Canada	2	7	AI/neuroscience, nanopublications, TIER project director, metadata modeling, neuroscience, teaching/reproducibility
4	Australia	Australia	1	0	Psychology
6	Oceania	New Zealand	1	0	Psychology
	Total		18	17	

Note. The “Area/Field of the people from that region” refers to the main scientific area or professional field represented by participants from that region.

Gender and Seniority level

The gender distribution was generally balanced, with 18 of the 35 participants being female, though as Figure 1 demonstrates, the females were on average less senior than the males. Figure 1 shows that men were more likely to be professors or outside of the academic system (e.g., developers, entrepreneurs) than the females who were most often Ph.D. students or PostDocs.

Figure 1

Sample Level of Employment

1 - Student or Master degree; 2 - Early Career Researchers; 3 - Postdoctoral Researchers; 4 - Professors and Senior Academics; 5 - Others, e.g. developers outside of academia, freelancers

Results

For comprehensibility, we go through each of our target questions, outlining the main and most interesting things we learned through these interviews. Specific quotes are worked in to highlight some common points, but in general we report on what we learned, for instance reporting on the different tools that the interviewees mentioned, the different practices in terms of naming their variables, and how they would like to see this area develop.

Below the sections are split into the following, "Experiences with Metadata", "Variable coding practices", "Coding schemes for meta.data", "Barriers to Standardization", and "Opportunities for Standard Templates".

1. Experiences with metadata

What does the concept of meta.data mean to the interviewees and how does metadata relate to the interviewees' work?

Concepts of metadata varied widely among interviewees. Students and researchers often viewed metadata at a basic level, focusing on the details of the dataset, such as who collected it, when, and what its content is. In contrast, those working on metadata standards and tool development viewed metadata as central to their work. A few have actually created tools for data care - for example, BIDS, Replication Wiki or Neurobagel. An interesting case is Kyle Husmann, who discussed the Frictionless standard, which allows tools to be created on a variety of development platforms and languages, including R, Python, etc.

Among researchers, Metadata are crucial for organizing and standardizing large, complex datasets, especially in interdisciplinary or internationally collaborative research. They simplify the interpretation of variables, reduce errors, and support data sharing and reproducibility, in line with open science principles.

There were also participants who used these tools in educational settings. In particular, they have taught classes on reproducibility and created guidelines for students on data preparation. Educators also use metadata tools to teach about reproducibility and guide students in preparing data for reuse. Experienced researchers tend to prioritize metadata more than those at the beginning of their careers, emphasizing its importance for future data use and collaboration.

I'm a big proponent of **reusing and recycling data**. And **for that to happen, obviously we need really good metadata** to be able to apply some data that has been gathered in a specific context into a different context.

So I believe that people have a lot of data that is not used and will probably never be used. So I firmly believe that that should be, **should be open**. As far as people are not afraid of, I don't know, using that. And so those, if you check on, **Open Science Framework** there are embargos, for example, for, for hypothesis...

How do interviewees make their datasets reusable to others?

Most participants pointed to repositories such as Zenodo, Open Science Framework (OSF) or institutional databases for data sharing. Others pointed to re3data.org containing more than 4,000 data repositories. However, choosing a repository to maximize openness was seen as a challenge, leading many to use institutional platforms or repositories popular in their fields. Links to datasets in articles remain a common way to locate shared data.

Research teams emphasized the need for universal metadata and documentation standards to ensure transparency, organization and reusability. They also pointed to consistent naming conventions for variables, including the use of English, which is not obvious given the need to tailor research content to respondents' language.

Almost all participants used codebooks or data dictionaries (often Excel-based) to explain variables. Some mentioned innovative solutions such as WikiData, which standardizes the coding of variables (e.g., the different ways of categorizing gender in wikidata <https://prop-explorer.toolforge.org/>) for potential generalization.

I think what we've tried to do is rapidly move to a situation where you're **providing some of this metadata as separate files in an open format**. But also in ways that are as simple as possible. So for example, trying to provide **a data dictionary** in which you sort of recapitulate or restate all of the variables in the spreadsheet. But ensuring that each of them comes with an explanation, a definition, a description of what's being provided and the relationship between you know one set of numbers and another

2. Variable coding practices

What are the most common variables in the interviewee's area?

The participants mentioned a wide variety of variables, which we have generally categorized into demographic, experimental, and measurement type variables. Demographic variables describe what is being studied e.g., the person. In the social sciences demographic questions might be age, gender, education level, ethnicity, socioeconomic status (SES), salary, place of residence, these are variables that are in many studies, but do not currently have well implemented standard encodings.

Experimental variables are not directly about the participant, but might be things like trial number, condition, location, the time of the day the data were collected. Again these are variables that

are likely to be across a wide range of datasets but that do not currently have strong standards in terms of how they are coded in specific datasets like statistical map types (e.g., T Statistic, Z Statistic) or standard space and participants' metadata.

Lastly, measurement type variables could be considered as measures of e.g., personality, self-esteem, or any other variables. The distinction is not entirely clear in all cases, but still appears to be useful. Variable examples were across a wide range of studies, from internet traffic data, to neural networks, to the location and findings of particular ecological cameras used to estimate animal populations.

Do interviewees use metadata guides or analysis scripts from external sources? If so, where do they look for them?

Interviewees make little use of off-the-shelf analytical scripts or standardized variables, and their use is not widespread. Spontaneous mention was made during the interviews of occasional use of metadata guides, particularly from large public datasets such as OpenNeuro, BIDS, the World Value Survey and the European Social Survey. These guides, which include code books and variable naming conventions, were appreciated by interviewees, who also emphasized the high standards of metadata in collections such as GESIS or the European Values Surveys with explicit codebooks.

On the other hand, the use of external analysis scripts is less common. Respondents, while often using tools such as R and Python, tend to create their own scripts rather than using off-the-shelf solutions. They rely mainly on tips received from colleagues, supervisors or promoters, which are informal, for analytical practices and variable management.

One key challenge is the lack of formal training in metadata management, leaving many researchers relying on internal guidelines or templates developed by research teams. An additional constraint is the time and effort required to adopt external standards, which often discourages their use. At the same time, interviewees expressed interest in co-creating or using standardized metadata templates and guides that could improve collaboration between teams and enable better data reuse (see Table 3).

How do interviewees name their variables? Is it the standard way in their field?

In labeling their variables, the general trend of the interviewees was toward brevity, even at the expense of clarity or uniqueness. For instance, interviewees tend to name variables using abbreviations or initial letters (e.g., "wb" for well-being, "wcf" for WeChat frequency). This is obviously problematic for reuse unless there is some codebook. The names are often influenced by the software limitations (e.g., Mplus). There were other voices, though, advocating for clarity or salience of the labels in the first place. However, these features are highly subjective and relying on them will lead to variability across datasets anyway. Still, it is a pretty clear suggestion that the systematic variable labels need to be quite brief, even if the VOI underlying it is not that brief or clear. In our original works (Buttliere, 2021) we have argued for using the last two digits of the year the variable was released in as a way to briefly add complexity to different versions of e.g., "se" or "wb" variables.

I think now what we're trying to do is just **use really straightforward words** but have individual variables within each column that look across a row, and that gives you the full information of the stimuli or the the dependent variable

(...) The function names are really **salient words**. They mean something to you when you read it

Of note, there were many different conventions used, and there was some reticence about the ability to enforce some particular standard. Standards should be community decided, and many participants recognized such would open up standard analysis scripts. Thus at least some suggested any potential standard should allow for naming style flexibility. In the Wikidata model, as mentioned by Daniel Mietchen, any variable label that the individual uses is fine so long as it ultimately leads back to the ultimately correct VOI. In this case there is a local variable label that is mapped in an attribute to the global variable label, like a DOI but for variables i.e., the VOI system. On the other hand, this adds another layer of complexity, and this might be solved simply through education, meaning that once the standard is developed, and there is a well agreed upon script using that standard, it will simply be used as standard and taught, and accepted, also because it can be used as a template and applied.

4. Coding schemes for meta.data

What is the specific coding scheme for metadata when creating datasets?

Most participants acknowledged that there were few or no good standards for how variables or datasets were labeled in their area. Most did not use a specific system, unless they were a part of that particular team. Still, the interviewees stated that they kept the variable labels generally the same across a series of studies, but most used no tools to facilitate this. Most often it was just the personal preference of the interviewee, but a few participants also mentioned that their labs had a set of recommended labels for variables that were often used across research projects, again these were more informal practices and analysis scripts than any particular tools that were helping them. Variable naming conventions vary widely in the field, with no universal system. Inconsistent naming across datasets causes confusion and requires additional effort for interpretation. Examples include identical abbreviations (e.g., “SES” for socioeconomic status or self-esteem) used for different constructs.

When explored further, even if those ‘in house’ standards were shared within the lab, they were rarely coordinated across collaboration teams so that they could e.g., share datasets and analysis scripts. It was mentioned as well that in the absence of any common or in house standard, consulting more experienced colleagues on how to organize one’s data was of great value.

So, there is no standard to organize statistic maps. But if, like, you're really, into the thing, you can **try to discuss with people** and **receive some advices on how to do it, properly**, like, how to name your data, how to organize your collections on Neurovault, **how to enter your metadata**, and I think that this is what people will do. Actually, that's what I do

Those participants that were in the social sciences often mentioned specific variables which have standard question wordings, like scales for well-being, life satisfaction, loneliness or nicotine dependence. This kind of data is often acquired through well laid out questionnaires, which come with standard handbooks or guidelines regarding the specific wording of questions, or the combination and interpretation of the scores. These handbooks, however, usually do not contain any suggestions on the variable coding or metadata management.

Participants with a background in economics pointed toward more government level data that is usually drawn from large databases of the World Bank or other institutions. Each group has their own set of labels that they use for their variables e.g. GDP, and the institutions are not using standard encodings, though perhaps translators can be built. This will be addressed further, in the section related

to metadata templates. Neuroscientists in turn referred to Brain Imaging Data Structure as the most commonly used standard. While it provides encodings for most of the neuroimaging data types, BIDS is more of a standard at the file structure level, and not at the specific variable level.

Among the meta.data tool makers, there was a sense that participants do not want to use any standards, and are even unlikely to use strict standards, simply given the complexity of the research endeavor. Thus, as Daniel Mitchen argued, there should be multiple ways of coding a variable and then any variable labels could be used as long as it points to the standard that it is e.g., gender56 to indicate a specific way of coding gender. This seems a bit more cumbersome than simply using gender56 as the label, because one needs to point to it somehow in a machine readable way. Still, it brings flexibility. In this case the metadata would not be on the data themselves, but linked to, which was also a solution presented by Ronen Tamari, where he was able to hover over a variable in his semantic network and it gave him a link to click on which led to a metadata file where everything is linked; but again this is large scale standard data e.g., internet traffic and api type things within a particular machine. Still the affordance is very interesting and could be applied generally.

Table 3

Table of standards that we encountered during the interviews along with where you can find more information.

Tool Name	Citation
Frictionless	Petti, S., & Karev, E., 2022
Data Documentation Initiative (DDI)	Ryssevik, J., 2001
Research Data Alliance (RDA)	Ball, A., Greenberg, J., Jeffery, K., & Koskela, R., 2016
Brain Imaging Data Standard (BIDS)	Gorgolewski, K., Auer, T., Calhoun, V. et al., 2016
Cognitive Atlas	Poldrack RA, Kittur A, Kalar D, Miller E, Seppa C, Gil Y, Parker DS, Sabb FW and Bilder RM, 2011
Teaching Integrity in Empirical Research (TIER)	Ball, R.J., 2023
Dublin Core	Weibel, S., Kunze, J., Lagoze, C., & Wolf, M., 1998
Metadata Object Description Standard (MODS)	Guenther, R.S., 2003
Neurobagel	Jahanpour, A., Armoza, J., Dai, A., Bhagwat, N., Urchs, S., & Poline, J.-B., 2023
Neuroimaging Data Model (NIDM) Vocabulary	Queder N et al., 2023
Replication Wiki	Höffler, J. H., 2014
Hierarchical Event Descriptor	Robbins, K., Truong, D., Appelhoff, S., Delorme, A., & Makeig, S., 2021
Neurodata without Borders	Teeters et al., 2015
PREP pipeline (EEG Analysis)	Bigdely-Shamlo N, Mullen T, Kothe C, Su K-M and Robbins KA, 2015
Systematized Nomenclature of Medicine (SNOMED)	Cornet, R., de Keizer, 2008
R markdown	Baumer, B., & Udwin, D., 2015
Wikidata	Vrandečić, D., & Krötzsch, M., 2014
R Tidyverse style guide	Wickham, H. (n.d.). Welcome The tidyverse style guide
Google's R style guide	Google's R Style Guide, n.d.
Interlacer	Husmann, K., Desmet, P., 2024

Most likely this is not an exhaustive list, but these are the tools and standards that individuals brought up in the interviews.

3. Problems

What were the problems the interviewees have encountered when using others' datasets?

For data creators, the main problems were related to properly documenting their work in a way that is not cumbersome. For those that reuse data the main problems are decoding the datasets and also recoding them so that the datasets work with any particular analysis script.

The most serious obstacle pointed out by the participants was the lack of any codebook or data dictionary accompanying the datasets whatsoever. In cases when these kinds of documents were present, inconsistent variable naming was often mentioned as an instance of flawed data curation. A recurring theme was also the lack of preprocessing steps records, e.g. the information on whether a given variable represents raw or preprocessed, say z-scored or logged, data. Similarly, missing information on the version of a measuring tool, e.g. a questionnaire or a scale was often referred to as a major source of confusion. These problems were exacerbated by language issues and alphabet diversity in non-English language datasets.

(...) in NeuroVault, when you upload your map, one metadata field that is mandatory is the cognitive paradigm that was used during the acquisition and then that was studied to obtain the statistic maps. And so, you could select your paradigm inside the list. But **lots of statistic maps were labeled as one or other. And so, it was impossible to use.**

Even if the datasets were complemented with clear documentation, the participants had difficulties combining them with other datasets due to the lack of standardization. Because of that the researchers often had to spend significant amounts of labor on recoding the variables. This process is also very error prone. There is a lack of consistency in how variables are named in different datasets, which can lead to confusion. For example, "SES" can represent different concepts in different contexts.

This relates more generally to the difficulties encountered when trying to cooperate with people using various (versions of) software. Oftentimes variable labels need to be coded in particular ways e.g., without periods, without underscores, or no punctuation at all. This makes it difficult to create true standards which meet everyone's needs and criteria, and reemphasize the need for packages that will translate between these different standards.

Key finding: Desire for standardization is demonstrated across the many tools.

This need for standardization is the core problem that the meta.data movement is trying to solve, as well as all of the meta.data standards and tools that were presented by participants. For instance, one participant works on a data harmonization tool called Neurobagel, which serves as a platform for standardizing annotation across neuroimaging datasets. Another initiative, introduced by Kyle Hussman, is the Interlacer R package which allows one to indicate different types of missing data in standard ways.

Well, so the main thing for us is that we want to describe the data that each of the different institutes in our different places have, **we want to describe the data with a consistent language.**

5. Barriers to Standardization

Why, in the interviewees' opinion, don't people use standard encodings for their variables?

The major hindrances we found to standard encodings were first a lack of awareness of the idea, and simply a lack of digital infrastructure for the project. Many researchers create variable names based on what makes sense to them personally, without considering the long-term reusability of their datasets, at least up until the last few years when the open data and reproducibility movements began.

Also there was a sentiment that the personal benefits of having standardized datasets are not salient enough. Many times when people ask to see your data it is a bad thing, because they are looking to see if something is wrong with it. Thus, it can make sense to make more salient the positive benefits, for instance to have the data be added to larger datasets which can then get one citations. Another issue is that there is little systematic incentive for standardizing data, e.g. the journals do not require new scales to be published with standard variable labels, for instance.

But we want to approach it **less from a perspective of finger wagging**, don't you know about FAIR? And why haven't you done FAIR yet? It's the right thing to do. We want to say, look, **you have a tangible benefit** every time you do this.

I think what's very important in order to promote this is to **advertise it as a help for the researcher**. If you put it as, ah, it's needed for science and it's better for transparency, people think, yeah, in general, that's good, but where what's in it for me? If you stress that it's also

helpful for the researcher himself or herself, that if they document their work better, then maybe it gets cited better, and they can understand it better in the future.

Participants suggested that researchers were unlikely to change how they analyze their data because it will take much training and time to do. On the other hand many of them were open to the idea that in the long run it would save them time and effort, if there was a culture of open analysis scripts. They also questioned whether the disciplinary difficulties could be overcome, with each community needing its own set of standards etc.

6. Opportunities for Standard Templates

How do the interviewees imagine ways that using metadata templates for commonly used variables could make their work easier?

Interviewees highlighted significant benefits of using metadata templates, particularly in reducing the time spent on cleaning and organizing data. Standardizing commonly used variables, especially demographic ones, was seen as a way to improve collaboration, enhance transparency, and streamline dataset preparation. Many participants emphasized that adopting standard variable labels would simplify locating and reusing datasets from repositories. Additionally, metadata templates could eliminate repetitive decisions, accelerate onboarding of new team members through clear structures, and automate routine tasks using predefined filters and AI integration.

There were some concerns about the privacy implications of opening up the data and making them so transparent, but most participants agreed the data are in principle there already, and that the benefits, especially with properly applied GDPR awareness, will far outweigh the potential costs.

Another difficulty was in actually checking the standard encodings, since many people will probably apply them improperly. This is why the future tools should be as simple to use as possible, minimizing the potential for error making. Additionally, we intend to build a tool that will check that the data to which the template is about to be applied matches with the template to some extent.

Possibly there is also an educational use case for the metadata templates. The participants involved in teaching mentioned that students often struggle with naming their variables in a clear and

consistent way. The templates could facilitate the process by allowing the students to create their variables in a quick and intuitive way.

Personally, I would be very receptive to having some templates to say, here is the way you would set up, not just a typical code script, but like you said, **here is how you would save metadata. Here is like a recommended system for doing that.** (...) And that would be something that I would even **include in my classes to teach my students** to say, here is a template. (...) Whether it would be receptive across others in my discipline, I think some people would, and some people wouldn't. **There would be some people that are very set in the way that they do analysis and the way they manage data.** And I think it would take a long time and a lot of convincing to get them to adopt a template.

If we are talking about guidance for the institution, let's say Institute of Psychology in universities, guys, it needs to be done, collectively. Right? So it need to be collectively shared files.

What do the interviewees feel are potential solutions to getting people to use standard encodings?

The biggest challenge that people saw was actually creating the variable templates, as well as making the people in general aware of them. Of course, changing how people analyze their data is important, but before people can change their methods, the tools need to be built.

Many participants found it difficult to imagine how the community would come to some conclusion and standard about how the variables should be coded. This could of course be left to the community, and we hope that the mechanism of making an analysis script and standard encodings open in a paper format will be enough of an incentive to bring in a few example communities to start and to set the standards according to those who put in the work to make their datasets and analysis scripts that were good enough to be widely adopted.

Key Finding: Education as the major implementation factor and inhibitor

Some of the interviewees were dedicated teachers in statistics and data science classes. They often noted that currently the problem is that many people are advanced in analysis techniques and they produce very complicated datasets, but they do not have decent enough knowledge on data

curation and so those datasets are difficult to reuse. A major way of changing this is teaching reproducibility classes which those participants already do at their universities, but also issuing guidelines and textbooks (e.g. [TIER](#) project in social sciences and Glasgow University in psychology, neuroscience and data science).

How would the interviewees establish metadata templates within their specific research area?

Most of the researchers agreed that someone simply needs to begin creating the templates within their area. There was some discussion that we could standardize some way to come to a standard, that is write a paper about how a community might efficiently come to some standard encoding the variables they used.

Some interviewees suggested that senior researchers or team leaders could develop templates and guide younger researchers in using them. This is similar in some sense to having the person who created the scale set some standards about how it should be coded into the dataset. The number of questions is already standard, along with the wording, and scale points, we argue that it can make sense to also set a standard variable label and e.g., missing indicator (Buttliere, 2021).

It is also important to keep in mind that the templates should be created based on the tools that have already been proven effective in their specific areas of research. A good example here is BIDS, which tries to point to existing standards like Cognitive Atlas as vocabulary sources.

So there are a few instances where BIDS in general will try to not reinvent the wheel. So if there is already a standard for this, our usual rule of thumb in BIDS is we point to that other standard and we say, use the terminology or the terms over there. So for example, for description of the task or the experimental paradigm, we refer to what's the Cognitive Atlas or the cognitive paradigm ontology.

Another thing that was mentioned in most of the interviews is that journals should have more strict requirements on the data that are submitted by researchers along with the paper. If publishing data with standard encodings was mandatory, people would use the existing standards more often. Some journals in Economics (e.g. issued by American Economic Association) already make steps towards this and have a data editor position who makes sure all the data submitted are properly

described and explained and that they are easy to reuse, but they do not enforce any standards as to how the variables should be encoded into the dataset, e.g., variable labels or missing indicators.

And, and as journals are demanding more, the awareness will move to the beginning, you know, of the research process. Now increasingly people will start work already knowing, Hey, in the end I have to produce the documentation required for other people to make this replicable. But not all, you know, not all, all journals require that as a standard.

I think any kind of guideline how to document data variables would be helpful. And I think this could be easily kind of promoted by certain institutions. For example, in the UK, there's an economics network for education of economists. And the initiative I mentioned in the US, Teaching Integrity and Empirical Research, I think that that would be an ideal candidate to work together.

From the interviewees' perspective, what kind of infrastructure would be needed to encourage people to use standard encodings? What would such a tool or service do?

Key Finding: There needs to be a meta.data template checking system.

An ideal infrastructure would include publicly accessible repositories or libraries where variable templates, datasets, and codebooks are shared in a standardized format. Many interviewees suggested that these repositories would benefit from a sort of a checking system that helps ensure the dataset being uploaded has a proper form and all the necessary attachments like codebooks etc. Tools that automatically suggest or enforce standardized variable names while entering inside the dataset data could also be useful.

that would even be just as simple as saying, before you upload, make sure you have done this. Have you done this? Check, check, check sort of thing, and then upload. Or you could have a software that checks for the variable names, whether they exist or don't exist, and format within the cells. And then if it doesn't have that format, then you could, ping back the kind of the upload and say, no. We're not uploading it.

When it comes to the templates, most participants agreed that they would need to be made available online, through a sort of public library of templates. There should also be some agreement on

the standard format in which the templates are provided. There was also much discussion about the need for tools to check that the data are actually matching the template.

At the same time the participants often stressed that, although standardized, the templates should allow for some flexibility in variable naming and metadata annotation. The argument for this was the perceived difficulty in convincing a substantial number of researchers to completely change their habits and stick to one, very strict way of encoding their variables. Therefore, when creating the future infrastructure for standard encodings we should aim at a reasonable trade-off between standardization and flexibility.

And, the problem is that EEG researchers are very opinionated about how they should preprocess EEG data. And, it's very hard to get them to agree that this should be done, that x should be done. And so we sat down and asked ourselves, what is the minimum amount of preprocessing that we could do without offending anybody so that they would actually use it? And, we were working with a very opinionated group of researchers, a very large group, and so they all had opinions on it. And so we narrowed it down to a few things, and, one of them was removal of line noise.

(...) I guess the one danger you've got is if you try and propose, here is like one standardized way of doing it. You, you obviously need like a certain critical mass of people using it and recommending it and knowing where to find it.

Additionally, the participants often suggested the need for translation tools so that different versions of e.g., the gender variable can be coded back and forth. Translators between these various templates and getting the particular variable translated back and forth will be important, otherwise it does not make that much sense to adopt the standards in the first place, if half the people choose one template and several other groups use other templates. This relates to an idea of using a large language model in a sort of AI-driven plugin, which would assist researchers in standardizing their variables. The plugin would recognize unstructured metadata and convert it into standardized formats through labeling, organizing, and filling metadata fields based on input data. A similar solution could also be applied to analysis scripts.

(...) there's got to be maybe a checker, a debugger that says you should really be writing all of these things out, wouldn't you like to do it this way? And ChatGPT or one of the other things might be a good assistant for telling people how to do that (...)

What features should any standardized template include, in the interviewees' view?

Many of our participants referenced some particular standard, such as BIDS, and often referred to these when determining which variables they should include. Others referenced some standard data, such as the results from representative samples, which can then determine that a particular metric is coded correctly, for instance.

A major theme was that standards need to be accessible across programming languages and software packages. In this sense, the Frictionless Data Package is a great example from Kyle Hussman and something that should probably be examined as something to build around, assuming that any developed standards should be able to work across platforms. Below we list the essential features of potential templates that have been proposed throughout the interviews:

Table 4: Features that researchers mentioned as important for any variable level (VOI) system.

Features of potential templates	
1	Variable name / Variable Object Identifier
2	Indication of minimum and maximum scores of the variable
3	DOI to the paper validating the variable e.g. in psychological questionnaires
4	What the values mean - e.g. Is 6 the highest or the lowest score?
5	How missing data is indicated, e.g. is it 'NA' or another away?
6	Preprocessing steps that have been done on the variable i.e., provenance.
7	Link to an example dataset,
8	Basic analysis algorithms or links to analysis scripts.
9	Links to visualization analysis scripts
10	Databases where more data like it can be found (e.g., all uses of the scale).
11	A link to a tool or way to check that the data conform to the standard.
12	Open place for comment and additional standards.

In general it seems researchers should include as much information about the data as possible.

Finally, the idea will be to have some tools that check that the metadata and standards are correctly implemented.

And specifically for an R library that would contain these things, you probably would want a function that says, well, once you have filled in the data in there, just press run, and then it analyzes and computes the data for you. But the algorithms behind that function should be described somewhere. (...) Then it could also include example datasets. Right? So in these papers, if you're lucky, you can download the open access psychometric data that has been used to validate the questionnaire. It could also include, so not only would you be able to analyze the data, but you could also visualize it in some ways. Right?

(...) what's important for the data scientists coming back to try and reuse that data is to understand some of those variables and then also to understand aspects of for example what a maximum score might be what a minimum score might be because the particular number might look you know either high or low in very different contexts

How do the interviewees imagine the ideal data reuse scenario? How could this be achieved?

There were many different particular reuse data scenarios, but essentially all participants agreed that it would be useful to standardize variables and share/ reuse analysis scripts. A key element is the development and implementation of universal metadata templates that provide consistent variable names, clear definitions, and detailed information on transformations and coding. Data should be openly available in central repositories with advanced search tools and compatibility with various analytical tools (e.g., SPSS, R, Python). Supporting comparisons across studies and cultures requires metadata with multilingual annotation and AI tools for generating documentation and detecting inconsistencies. Educating researchers on best practices and introducing incentives such as funding and recognition further promote a culture of collaboration and transparency in science. As a result, datasets can be easily integrated, analyzed and applied to a variety of research and cultural contexts.

Essentially all participants also agreed that repositories should be searchable and would be easier to search if the meta.data and e.g., variable labels for particular variables were standardized. To this extent there was interest in the VOI system developed in Buttlere 2021, 2023, whereby individual variables are assigned unique Variable Object Identifiers (VOIs) which allow them to be uniquely searched for and identified. The question is whether anyone will really pick it up, and this is to be determined.

In most of the scenarios the researchers have a way for thoroughly describing what they have done in their experiments, i.e. they can store maximum amounts of metadata with minimum effort, within or attached to their datasets. This metadata is both human- and machine readable and thus is easy to reuse by other scientists in replications or big-data analyses.

Can the interviewees see themselves using metadata templates and standard analysis scripts? How and why would they use them?

Our interviewees did see value in using metadata templates and standard analysis scripts, especially if they make data analysis faster and improve consistency. The big question is how to establish them and get scientists using them. One participant hesitated because they doubted the feasibility of getting people to agree compared to the ease of existing solutions. This participant did not have any specific criticisms other than they thought researchers would not use standards.

It's an attitude thing, not a technical thing. I think, and I'm not sure, but perhaps, you know, perhaps there could be some tools which then may, which makes that easier to do, which I may not have seen, but I'm not, you know, I haven't really looked for anything there because I, I think it's really not that difficult to actually do it just by writing down the right documentation.

(...) I would be very interested to see what it could look like. I think I genuinely think this could have a big impact in sort of harmonizing the the way that we analyze data in psychology

(...) I think I think, the potential is that the templates provide a useful starting point.

What variables would the interviewees most value templates for? Would they be willing to help create them?

Interviewees would value templates for demographic variables (age, gender, education level), standard scales (well-being, life satisfaction), and variables related to online platform usage. Many expressed willingness to help create these templates, especially if it leads to more efficient and transparent research practices. Basically, for any type of variable that would be expected to be used by many people, our participants thought there would be benefits to making available a template.

Would the interviewees like to help develop common metadata templates for their field?

The interviewees are generally open to the idea of helping develop common metadata templates and several were discussing already ways to work such templates into their own work.

what we may have, just so that the ones who educate and the ones who work with the data and the ones who provide the data over together become aware and they get help so that it's easier for them to prepare data and to exchange data and to to use it in teaching and research.

I think for your purposes, frictionless is really great because it's very simple. There's existing infrastructure out there that reads it, and it's very extendable. Mhmm. And so it's very flexible to, so you can you can come up with, you know, what are the attributes that you wanna have in your template, and then you can, you can then create these schemas, which then, people can put in their frictionless data packages and start using.

Discussion

The interviews provided a wide range of viewpoints on the meta.data topic, from the humanities, ecology, and biology, to neuro and economic sciences. We additionally were able to interview representatives from many of the major teams in these areas, which gives insight into what is going on at the very cutting edge of the field.

Most of our interviewees did not use formal metadata guides or analysis scripts from external sources. Instead, they created their own codebooks and relied on internal practices or advice from supervisors. However, many of the interviewees expressed interest in tools like the meta.data()R package that could automate some aspects of metadata management, and the use and potential value of standardizing particular variable labels and creating templates was clear to essentially everyone we interviewed.

Two major dimensions developed out of the interviews, the social-organizational and the technical one. These also paired with the concerns that emerged, those being communicating across different programming standards, and getting people to use the standards. To this end we believe something like the Frictionless data standard can be used as a basis, so that different programming environments are not a problem. We additionally believe that once some standards are built, people will start adopting them, given the wide range of interest across the many disciplines that we found. Our next goal will be to establish some basic demographic variables and begin making these available to researchers.

These results confirm many of the current results in the area, but also push in new directions, especially in the need for education in this area so that students know the templates exist and how to use them. Projects like this bring field and thought leaders together, not only to identify the very edge of the idea, but also to hopefully collaborate together in the future on this topic. Without further ado, we highlight our main conclusions from these interviews:

Researchers like the idea of standardizing meta.data at the variable level.

In general, we found enthusiasm for the idea of standardizing data at the variable level. Participants understood the concepts involved, the mechanisms needed, and could see how such an initiative could improve the transparency of the field. Nearly all participants foresaw the need to

standardize encoding of variables. Most participants also agreed that this will allow for more standard analysis scripts. There were some concerns about the actual feasibility of getting people to agree on specific codings, but essentially everyone agreed that it could in principle be beneficial if communities could share analysis scripts, which necessitates standardizing. There appear to exist few standardizations at the variable level. When we presented our own solution, essentially everybody agreed that more standards, especially as they relate to reusing analysis scripts, will be beneficial.

Digital infrastructure needed to potentiate templates and standard analysis scripts.

Based on the interviews we have had, a vision for a set of tools can be drawn. a) The metadata templates essential for the research fields b) a tool for creating the metadata templates c) a library to host the templates and make them available online d) some tool to check that the templates are used correctly. Most likely a key next step will be to build some sort of online library which researchers can access to identify specific variables according to their VOI.

Another major goal of the next years is to establish some educational programs in this area. This will be more of a train the trainers type event, and the idea is that it will be given to students as they engage with research. Creating and sharing standardized templates within research teams and encouraging their use through formal training will be key solutions. Additionally, we expect to establish a norm where new scales are published with some standard meta.data templates already established, along with e.g., a requested repository to put new datasets so that they can be added to e.g., worldwide metaanalyses. Providing guidelines or standardized codebooks with publications could also help spread the practice.

Limitations of the current study

While the project has very interesting results, we only interviewed 35 individuals, and so cannot claim to have complete knowledge of this area or e.g., existing tools or databases. We additionally did not do much e.g., text analysis of the interviews, which could lead to some systematic or unrecognized insights being missed. Another potential limitation is that because the participants in our study were identifiable, and indeed we told them that we intend to release the interviews as a part of the project, it is possible that they did not tell us their most truthful responses. Another limitation of

the study was that all interviews were conducted in English, which obviously limits the potential interviewees and thus global representation.

Conclusion

After conducting these interviews with a wide range of actors, we are convinced that there is a lack of tools developing standard variable labels and meta.data, as well as an interest in building these affordances for the future. The variable level template seems to be a potential solution, but participants also believed it could be difficult to get participants to agree on e.g., what should be in that meta.data. The three main problems for the next few years appear to be agreeing upon the standards that will be used, actually creating templates for commonly used variables, and making the community aware that they exist and are available.

Declarations:

Ethics approval and consent to participate: The project was reviewed by the National Center for Science, the University of Warsaw, and EUROREG and was approved to do. Additionally, all participants knew that the interviews were intended to be released on youtube as a part of a podcast when they agreed to the interview.

Consent for publication: The authors declare that they have and give permission to the journal to print the paper.

Availability of data and material: All of the videos and transcripts for the interviews are made available at the OSF link osf.io/xe985

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Authors' contributions: CREDIT Statement:

- **Remigusz Depta** helped develop the questions that were being asked, was responsible for contacting, recruiting, and interviewing 15 of the participants, and helped transcribe and analyze the data, including reading the transcripts for accuracy. He also helped draft the paper.
- **Anna Gajda** helped develop the questions that were being asked, she was responsible for contacting, recruiting, and interviewing 15 of the participants, and helped transcribe and analyze the data, along with reading the transcripts for accuracy. She also helped draft the paper.
- **Tomasz Kupiec** was responsible only for transcribing the interviews using Turboscribe and drafting the paper.
- **Brett Buttiere** was responsible for conceptualizing the project and gathering the funds to run the project, hiring Remigusz and Anna, guiding the development of the interview protocol and overseeing the analysis or results and writing of the paper. He also contacted, recruited, and interviewed 5 participants.

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